

IoT Based Smart Traffic Cone System

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Abstract:

Chain reaction vehicle accidents are the common type of accidents that occur especially on highway roads. This is caused by several factors including crossing the speed limit, sometimes drivers are not aware about the traffic movement when it is stopped in places, conditions that are not expected to them also if the road is not safe to be drive on, for example because of bad weather, especially during rainy season which can cause the road to be slippery, or it can increase the water level in the road to a point that is difficult to drive. The **IoT Based Smart Traffic Cone System** aims to provide a solution for the above issues by using different types of sensors and IoT technologies which all will be presented in the form of a traffic cone. The device is portable and solar powered so can be placed anywhere. The traffic cones will be placed in the middle of the highway between the ingoing and outgoing roads, the IR sensors will sense if the traffic movement is stopped, then it will send a signal to the Flashing Red LED at the top of the cone to turn it on, to alert the drivers about the road status, otherwise a green LED light will be on. A traffic display panel will be placed before the traffic cone, so that the drivers can make an action before they get to the place where there is a traffic jam. The maximum distance between the cone and the wireless display panel is 20 meters. Another sensor called moisture sensor, will sense the presence of water in the road, if the amount of water in the road is high and is difficult to drive, the device will activate the flashing Blue LED which represent the water issues that is in the road, Buzzer will also be activated and the Red LED light will be turning on in the LED Display panel. The ROP (Royal Oman Police) can monitor the status of the smart traffic cones and can activate/deactivate the system remotely using an application through the internet, and if two to three sensors detect an issue on the road it will inform the ROP controller. RoP can monitor the road status and the surroundings of the cones using a camera. As per the **VISION 2040 of OMAN** Smart and sustainable cities are to be built with advanced IT infrastructure. This is an innovative idea developed with the suggestions and recommendations from RoP for the smart city development. With continuous research and study we will develop the prototype of the system.

Keywords: IoT, Raspberry Pi, IR Sensor, LED, **Moisture** sensor, Buzzer